

Review Article

Female Entrepreneurs' Business Performance's "Up – Scaling" Contending With Business Environment

Shefiu Raheem

Department of Business Administration, School of Business and Entrepreneurship,
American University of Nigeria, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria. bestraheems@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to examine business environment and how female entrepreneurs mitigates its impact in up-scaling their performance in order to return their businesses to the path profitability and its attendant economic prosperity. Female entrepreneurs are simply females that participate in total entrepreneurial activities, who take the risks involved in combining resources together in a unique way so as to take advantage of the opportunity identified in their immediate environment through production of goods and services. The environment of going concerns, like the habitats of animals, contributes to their development. Like the natural environments of living beings, the environment of a business can either enhance or stifle its growth and development. The nature and extent of the impact of the environment on any company depends on the internal configuration of such a company. It has been a vital point to consider in evaluating entrepreneurial performance, researches have established that there is relationship between entrepreneurial activity and the environment in which it is domiciled. The proper understanding of the social, political, legal and economic environment will help the female entrepreneur to determine opportunities and threats to her business. The environmental analysis of female entrepreneurs makes the tasks of female entrepreneurs easier in dealing with business challenges, image building and meeting with competition to achieve performance and growth. The interaction between the business and its environment is therefore imperative to give direction for growth and expansion of the entrepreneurships business showing their sensitivity to the environment within which they are domiciled. The World Bank is of the opinion that improvements in the enabling environment of the female entrepreneur leads to greater levels of investment by the private sector, more wealth, job creation, and ultimately more poverty alleviation.

KEYWORDS: Business Environment, Female Entrepreneurs, Business Performance, Economic Prosperity

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Introduction

Female entrepreneurs are simply females that participate in total entrepreneurial activities, who take the risks involved in combining resources together in a unique way so as to take advantage of the opportunity identified in their immediate environment through production of goods and services. Most of them are involved in micro, small and medium scale enterprises (MSMEs) which contribute more than 97% of all enterprises, 60% of the nation's GDP and 94% of the total share of the employment (Ndubusi, 2004). The spectrum of women in entrepreneurship often ranges from home-based businesses (HBB) to micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSEs) (ILO, 1998). Women entrepreneurs generally share the same motivations with their men counterparts. They operate within a dynamic business environment

The word "Environment" in management, does not necessarily mean physical surroundings, but is used to describe all those influences that bear upon the individual organizations. Business environment is used to mean anything, which surrounds the business organization. It connotes external forces, factors and institutions that are beyond the control of the business and they affect the functioning of a business enterprise. These include customers, competitors, suppliers, government, and the social, political, legal and technological factors etc. While some of these factors or forces may have direct influence over the business firm, others may operate indirectly. Thus, business environment may be defined as the total surroundings, which have a direct or indirect bearing on the functioning of business. It may also be defined as the set of external factors, such as economic factors, social factors, political and legal factors, demographic factors, and technical actors which are uncontrollable in nature and affects the business decisions of a firm.

It affects the decisions, strategies, process and performance of the business. The environment is consisting of factors which are beyond the control of the business (STEP) social, technological, economical, legal and political. It provides opportunities or poses threats to the organization. Since business makes demand on the society and the society makes demands on the business, managers in any organization must interact with and respond to environmental factors internal or external to their organizations. The sum of these interrelationships within the business and between the business and the society is what in management is regarded to as business environment.

Business environment is the combination of physical and social factors that is reflected in the individual organization (Duncan, 1972). In management, the word "Environment" does not necessarily mean physical surroundings, but is used to describe all those

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influences that bear upon the individual organizations. Business environment is used to mean anything, which surrounds the business organization. It affects the decisions, strategies, process and performance of the business. The environment is consisting of factors which are beyond the control of the business (STEP) social, technological, economical, legal and political. It provides opportunities or poses threats to the organization.

The modern business manager operates in a more dynamic environment. The change in the environment has been rapid and unpredictable. Economic variables have been complex both in form and impact on the practice of business in Nigeria. Business Environment consists of all those factors that have a bearing on the business, such as the strengths, weaknesses, internal power relationships and orientations of the organization; government policies and regulations; nature of the economy and economic conditions; socio cultural factors; demographic trends; natural factors; and, global trends and cross-border developments.

The firm interacts with its environment. There are in fact different levels of environment, each encompassing several components. Thus, the environment of the firm consists of several environments. Environment as a general term refers here to all those arenas the firm is operating in and is attached to (Okafor and Mordi, 2010). Moreover, environments and their components affect firm performance in many ways, directly or indirectly (Ishola and Adeola, 2015).

Business environments of an enterprise are events which directly or indirectly affect the operations of enterprise and they are uncontrollable. He said the business environment can be grouped into task environment which is well defined and example is customers, suppliers, bankers etc and the general external business environment which is defined and can be conceptualized as PESTEL (Akrofi, 2016).

Business environment has two components; internal environment and external environment. Micro and macro environments are two components of the external environment in the business environment. Micro environment constitute of the forces which are close to the company and affect its ability to work. Macro forces means general environment of the business. Macro forces are uncontrollable in comparison to the micro forces of the business environment (Jain et al., 2009)

Since business makes demand on the society and the society makes demands on the business, managers in any organization must interact with and respond to environmental factors internal or external to their organizations. The sum of these interrelationships

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within the business and between the business and the society is what is the management regarded as business environment. Organizations survival and success depend on the appropriate adoptions to a complex and over changing environment. As a concept, business environment is regarded to be a complex and important consequent, the concept has been addressed in a number of ways by different scholars (Eruemenbe, 2015). Business environment (BE) is the set of norms and ethics, legal and governing frameworks, and the overall policy conditions that set rules for conduct of business, and influence positively or negatively the outcome of markets, flow of investment, factor productivity, and the cost of doing business, these can either be from both internal or external settings and affect the smooth operation and function of an organization (Alekhugie, 2014).

Objective of the Study

- To explain why female entrepreneurship would always take place within the confines of business environment in Nigeria.
- To identify the components of business environment of female entrepreneurs in Nigeria.
- To identify entrepreneurship within the female entrepreneurs' environment and consequently leverage on it for wealth creation.

Research Methodology

This paper adopted a qualitative research design which entailed a critical review of literature on the roles of women entrepreneurship in economic growth and development and it could be deployed effectively to emancipate the womenfolk from excruciating poverty as a result of their entrepreneurial failures. The study adopted a conceptual approach. The use of systematic literature review

External Environment

The external environment is a set of complex that rapidly changing and significant interacting institutions and forces that affect the organization's ability to serve its customers.

External forces cannot be controlled by an organization but they may be influenced by that organization. It has a major impact on the determination of marketing decisions. Successful organizations scan their external environment so that they can respond profitably to unmet needs and trends in the targeted markets (Reddy, 2004).

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External Environment

Source: Xu et al. (2011).

Figure 1: External Environment picture depicting how business operates

Figure 1 shows the overall environment in which the business operates consists of wider external environment with segments such as: political and legal, economic, demographic, socio-cultural, technological, international and narrower external environment with segments such as: customers, suppliers, competitors and substitutes (Akinbami, 2015).

The external environment consists of all the outside institutions and forces that have an actual interest on the organization's ability to achieve its objectives like: competitive, economic, technological, political, legal, demographic, cultural, and ecosystem (Jain et al., 2009). Construction business in Albanian tries to response to these forces in order to keep positive actions with the targeted markets (Akinbami, 2015).

It is all events outside the company that has the potential to affect the company (Chuck, 2001: 51). Many companies are now competing in a global market, not only in the domestic market. Changes in technology and increased ability to acquire and process information requires the implementation and competing responses are more timely and

effective. Rapid sociological changes that occur in many countries affects employment, in addition to the desired product properties consumers increasingly varied. Policies and laws that affect the government outlined the company's choice of where and how they will try and compete. Companies should be alert and aware of the impact of the reality of this environment, so it can be an effective actor in the global economy (Ibrahim and Primiana, 2015)

It is a contingent factor that cannot be overemphasized by the firm as regards the role that is played by the environment in its operations on in terms of the opportunities it creates and the threats it poses. This is captured in the various types of risks that the firm faces because of the impending threats and opportunities that arise from the firm's external environment. These risks are a function of the complexity and uncertainty associated with the environment which can have a significant impact on a firm's success. Duncan (1972) viewed external business environment as the totality of factors outside an organisation that are taken into consideration by an organisation in its decision making. These factors (Table 1) depend largely on the complexity and dynamism of the environment (Duncan, 1972). Thus, external business environment has been classified as being stable when it does show any changes, unstable when it shows relative changes, and dynamic when it shows changes continuously (Figure 2).

MACRO ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS.

Table 1: Macro Environmental Factor

Sector	Content	Examples	
General Environment	Economic	Macroeconomic indicators	Interest rates, inflation rates
		Financial indicators	Stock markets, bond markets
		Price/cost trends	Cost of outputs, cost of inputs
	Sociocultural	Demographic trends	Population growth, median ages
		Societal perceptions	Attitudes to large companies
	Regulatory	Legal issues	Direct and indirect regulation
Political considerations		Government activity, political issues	
Task Environment	Customer	Customers	Individuals, companies, other groups
		Potential customers	As above
	Competitive	Competitors	Resource and customer competition
		Indirect competitors	Possible substitutes
		Suppliers	Competition for resources
	Technological	Technological development	New technologies
Technological opportunities		Technically viable opportunities	

LAYERS OF BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT

Source: Johnson et al. (2008)

Figure 2. Layers of Business Environment

MACRO BUSINESS ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Macro environment means general environment of the business. Macro environment consists of all the outside institutions and factors that have an actual or potential interest on the organization's or construction industry's ability to achieve their objectives like: economic, technological, political, legal, demographic, and cultural (Jain et al., 2009).

According to Philip Kotler; "Macro environment includes factors that create opportunities and pose threat to the business units. It includes economic, demographic, natural, technological, political and cultural environments" (Jain et al., 2009).

These are broad business environment factors that have bigger or less impact on almost all firms (Johnson et al., 2008). According to Itani et al., (2011) macro business environment where a firm finds itself in can influence the performance of that firm and the rate of influence depends on what share of the firm's depending on the overall economy. PESTEL framework which consists of political, economical, socio-cultural, technological, environmental and legal is used to analyze the macro environment, (Akrofi, 2016).

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POLITICAL ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Political environment is any national or international political factors that can affect the performance of SMEs positively or negatively (Wanjiru et al., 2013). It includes government subventions for national carriers, security controls, boundaries on migration, etc. (Johnson et al., 2008). Political imperatives are spot on SMEs through duty modified, the lowest pay permitted by law enactment, contamination approaches and different activities went for securing workers, clients, the overall population and nature. Nevertheless, some political actions are planned to give benefits and protect SMEs. Such laws include patent laws, government subventions and product research incentives (Akrofi, 2016).

ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Economic factors include the general economic climate, trade rates, inflation rate, labour unemployment rate, interest rates, the rate of economic development, per capita domestic product and trade deficit or surplus (Gamble et al., 2014).

Economic factors help SMEs to make strategic decision. It is important for entrepreneurs of Small and Medium Sized Enterprises in pharmaceutical industry to comprehend monetary elements and indicators and to utilize the information to help marketing decision-making and planning process. For instance, if there is a variation in interest rates, then it is likely that SMEs may be involved in considering increases in cost. According to Related and Rights, 2007 stated that high trade barriers in Ghana leads to high local production cost of pharmaceutical products which affect the local drugs not to be competitive with the imported drugs (Akrofi, 2016).

TECHNOLOGICAL ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Technological forces refer to the rate of scientific change and fastest growth of technology that have potential wide-ranging effects on society (Gamble et al., 2014). Technological factors have rendered some SMEs not competitive and not able to meet the needs of customers. However, entrepreneurs in Small and Medium Scale pharmaceutical industry need to recognize the need for technological change, and the need to go with the flow, to have competitive advantage. Decisions to improve change or implement new technological processes must be made in order to meet customer wants and needs. Information Technology has been identified as a major player in innovation and competitiveness of SMEs but according to European Union (EU), a full potential of IT will be harnessed if labour force is equipped with right skills and having access to high-tech infrastructure (Akrofi, 2016).

LEGAL ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Legal environment forces include, labour law, antitrust laws, regulations, occupational health and safety policies and other laws of a country or pertaining to particular business environment that industry within the business environment must with those rules. In Ghana, the cumbersome procedures and commencing businesses were issues affecting local entrepreneurs in pharmaceutical whole sale and retail industry (Akrofi, 2016).

ENTREPRENEURSHIP WITHIN THE ENVIRONMENT.

The actual indication of the functions and roles of entrepreneurship in socio-economic development have often been attributed to the presence of certain factors in the external environment of the entrepreneur over which he has little or no jurisdiction. Borkowski and Kulzick (2006), list the interaction between entrepreneurship and environment as follow:

- new venture strategies are formed in response to environmental forces
- entrepreneurs are negative towards and will resist political interference
- unstable environments are negatively related to growth opportunities.

There has been an assortment of viewpoint put up to scrutinize the links between entrepreneurial activities and the environment. Outstanding among these is the work of Thornton (1999) who attributed entrepreneurial activities in a society to the following explanations; Supply-side and Demand-side perspectives. The supply-side perspective emphasizes the role of individuals in creating entrepreneurial environment. According to Thornton (1999) the supply-side, holds that “special types of individuals create entrepreneurship”. This is further linked to economic development or underdevelopment. This perspective attributes economic development of any society to an adequate supply of ‘special’ individuals with traits that are well-matched with entrepreneurial practices.

An entrepreneur is also expected to classify business prospects as well as taking the risk of utilizing the business opportunities. A business depends on its environment for the supply of all its input and at the same time absorbs the output of the business enterprise. The environment provides opportunities for alternative investment which the business manager can exploit to his or her advantage. On the other hand, the environment could start a threat or constraint. For a business to survive in the long run it must be seen as coping, adapting, and responding favorably to the environment it operates in (NCPE, 2012). Changes in the external environment of a business may induce a change in the strategy, structure, technology or the nature of human resources that the firm employs, into the business enterprise if changes in it are unfavorable.

FEMALE ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Mansor (2005) enumerated these factors, namely: venture capital availability, presence of experience, technical skilled labour force, accessibility of suppliers, customers, new markets, government influences, land, transportation, new technological development, supporting services and living condition. ILO (2003) regards environment factors as the external factors that include: (i) government policy (fiscal and legislative framework), (ii) access to appropriate business development support, (iii) access to finance and financial services and (iv) community and family.

NIGERIAN BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT

Ola (1993) classified Nigerian business environment as the Nigerian economy since the businesses are established and managed within an economy. He was of the opinion that the state of affairs has a significant on the business within that economy.

Oyebanji (1994) further testified that Nigerian business environment has witnessed a total change, which started from the oil boom era in 1960s austerity measure in the early 70's and structural adjustment programme in the 80s.

Aldrich (1979) said the environment was made up of stable and unstable homogenous, heterogeneous, rich and poor, complex and simple, unpredictable variables. He further stressed that business environmental factors change along with factors of production and environmental influences may be stable over a certain period of time.

The assertion was supported by Van de Van (1986), which had the view that the manager's basic role is to be able to manage and control the organization in the difficult and emergency period. Changes take the form of adaptation. The manager must perceive the process and respond to a changing environment by re-arranging the internal organization structures so as to ensure survival and effectiveness. The need for studying business environment is important considering the fact that business organization do not operate in a vacuum, effective management to complex and dynamic society requires the assessment of strength and weakness of the organization and the opportunity and threat posed by the challenges of the external environment. For survival and growth, organization must adapt these changes.

The Nigerian business environment has witnessed a lot changes from the period of the oil boom in the 1960s and the early 1970s. Austerity measures in the early 1980s and the structured adjustment programme in the late 1980s from the company act of 1960s allied matter decree in the 1990s, undoubtedly brought in the eighty's the opportunities to be

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exploited by some firms or the problems that inhibit the survival of so many business firm.

The need for studying business environment became important considering the fact that business organization do not operate in vacuum and effective management in complex and dynamic society such as Nigeria, requires the assessment of strengths and weaknesses of the organization and the opportunities and threats posed and the challenges of the external environment by the challenges of the external environment. For survival and growth, organization must adapt to these changes

CONCEPT OF BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

The concept of performance is used to determine the success of a business entity whether small, medium or big. Firm performance refers to the firm's success in the market, which may have different outcomes. Firm performance is a focal phenomenon in business studies. However, it is also a complex and multidimensional phenomenon. Performance can be characterized as the firm's ability to create acceptable outcomes and actions. However, performance seems to be conceptualized, operationalized, and measured in several ways. Business Performance Measurement then is concerned with measuring this performance relative to some benchmark, be it a competitor's performance or a preset target. Performance is the act of performing; or doing something successfully; using knowledge as distinguished from merely possessing it (Salihu et al., 2015)

BUSINESS PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT

The selection of performance measures that reflect the true situation of small businesses with some degree of certainty and reliability is indeed a crucial process. The lack of universally accepted standard performance measures left the door open to business organizations to decide and choose its own performance measure that might not truly reflect its performance. Such performance measures include but not limited to: market share, sales volume, company reputation, return-on-investment (ROI), profitability, and established corporate identity. While some might argue that most of these performance measures are appropriate for large corporations, they are not always perfectly applicable to small businesses.

One performance measure that is widely used among small businesses, as a subjective indicator of the overall business performance is the degree of owner/manager satisfaction with the business performance. Adequate income, job satisfaction, a happy workforce, and a stable market position are all factors that lead to small business owners"/managers" satisfaction.

Another valid performance measure is turnover. Turnover growth is an objective measure that is relatively easy to get due to data availability and common use and is also a good indicator of firm size and a proxy for overall business growth. There is a wide range of measures of organizational performance in the literature. Often, performance has been measured by growth (turnover, number of employees, market share), profitability (e.g. profit, return on investment), and survival.

Conclusion

The theories about management and organization emphasized linkages between business environment and organization performance. The organization performance can be improved through increases in the business environment. The business environment is a system and structure which determine the atmosphere where all the businesses of the industry are operated. Internal and external environment are two components of the business environment. Internal environment includes internal factors of the business that can be controlled by the business. External environment consists of all outside forces that have an actual interest on the business's ability to achieve its objectives. External forces are not able to be controlled by the organization but they may be influenced by that organization. Micro and macro environment are two types of the external environment. Environment whether conducive or non-conducive has a significant influence on entrepreneurial development. While conducive environment will result in 'pull' factors that could encourage or lure women into entrepreneurship, non-conducive environment will result in 'push' factors which could also force or push women into business.

Finally, the government should create a friendly or an enabling environment for entrepreneurship and consumer goods in order to boost the economy, as entrepreneurship is an employment strategy that can lead to economic self-sufficiency for the people. It makes nationals create and manage businesses in which they function as the employer or boss rather than merely being an employee. Every country aims at achieving self-sufficiency through producing what the country needs. A government must encourage industries to enhance production to satisfy internal and external demands and to achieve considerable improvement in entrepreneurship performance.

References

Adim. C., Tamunomiebi, M.D., Akintokunbo, O.O (2018). Innovativeness and Performance of Women Entrepreneurs' in Rivers State, Nigeria. *World Journal of Entrepreneurial Development Studies*. 2(1), 9-23

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ISSN: 2251 - 0486 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Akinbami, C.A.O. (2015). Assessing the Implications of Book-Keeping and Payment Culture on Sustainable Female Entrepreneurship Development in Osun State, Nigeria. *Ife Social Sciences Review*, Vol. 24(2), 71-95

Akrofi, A.E. (2016). The Impact of External Business Environment Factors On performance of Small & Medium Sized Enterprises in the pharmaceutical Industry in Kumasi Metropolis. MSc. Thesis submitted to Department of Marketing and Corporate Strategy Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology School of Business. School of Business, KNUST College of Humanities and Social sciences. Ghana.

Aldrich, H. (1979). *Fundamental as Moderate of Job Satisfaction*, New York; Random House Incorporation.

Alekhugie, N. (2014) "Challenges before Female Entrepreneurs in Nigeria" *Thisday Newspaper* 8th July.

Borkowski, N. and Kulzick, R. (2006). Perspectives from the Field: Will Recent Public Policies Reduce Entrepreneurship in the Healthcare Industry? *International Journal of Public Administration*. 29(7), 479-488. 10.1080/01900690500452294

Chuck, W. (2001). *Effective Management: A Multimedia Approach*. Cengage Learning. Page 21

Duncan, R. B. (1972). Characteristics of Organizational Environments and Perceived Environmental Uncertainty. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 17(3), 313-327. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392145>

Eruemegbe, G.O. (2015). Impact of Business Environment on Organization Performance in Nigeria-A Study of Union Bank of Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*. November 2015 /SPECIAL/ Edition. 478-494.

Gamble, J., Thompson, A., Peteraf, M. (2014). *Essentials of Strategic Management: The Quest for Competitive Advantage* Paperback. 4th edition. Burr Ridge, IL: McGraw-Hill. p.480

Ibrahim, R and Primiana, I (2015). Influence Business Environment on the Organization Performance. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research* Volume 4(4), 283-293

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2251 - 0486 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

International Labour Organisation (1999). Key indicators of the labour market (KILM). ILO, Geneva, Switzerland

Ishola, O.A and Adeola, A. (2015). A Survey of the Barriers of Women Entrepreneurs in Akure City of on do State, Nigeria. Volume 1(7), 1-10

Itani, H., Sidani, Y. M. and Baalbaki, I. (2011). United Arab Emirates Female Entrepreneurs: Motivations and Frustrations. Equality Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal, 30, (5), 409-424

Jain. R.T, Trehan Mukeshand Trehan Ranju (2009). Business Environment, Meaning of Business, Published by Rahul Jain, V.K (INDIA) Enterprises, New Delhi: 3-28

Johnson, G., Scholes, K. and Whittington, R. (2008) Exploring Corporate Strategy: Text and Cases. 8th Edition, Prentice Hall, Harlow.

Mansor, N. (2005) Women in Business: Determinants for Venturing in Malaysians SMEs. www.tbs.ubbc/uj.ro/studia/articol_4_2_2005.

National Commission for Promotion of Equity (NCPE) (2012) "Entrepreneurs and Vulnerable Workers in Malta: Unleashing the Female Potentials" NCPE, pp. 64- 120.

Ndubusi, F. (2004). Bankers List Financing Alternatives for SMEs, in CBN Seminar on Small and Medium Industries Equity Investments Scheme, Maritime.

Okafor, C. and Mordi, C. (2010). Women Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria. The Effect of Environmental Factors. Petroleum-Gas University of Ploiestii, Bulletin, Lxii, pp.43-52

Ola, C. (1993). Nigerian Business Environment: Lagos; Published by Abiola Bookshop Limited.

Oyebanji, J. (1994). Nigerian Business Environment and Organization Effectiveness; Abiola Bookshop Limited.

Reddy Jayaprakash. R. (2004). Business Environment, Published in India by S.B Nangia, A P H Publishing Corporation, New Delhi: 1-6

Salihu, I.A, Annuar, H.Z., and Obid, S.N.S. (2015), Foreign investors' interests and corporate tax avoidance: Evidence from an emerging economy, Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics, **11**, (2), 138-147

Thornton, S. (1999). Creating the conditions for cognitive change: The interaction between task structures and specific strategies. *Child Development*, 70(3), 588-603. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00043>

Van De Ven, A. H. (1986). Central Problems in the Management of Innovation. *Management Science*, 32(5), 590-607. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.32.5.590>

Wanjiru, K. (2013) Education: A Right Or A Privilege? The Kenyan Perspective Journal of Education Management. 1(1), 1-15

Xu, B., Li, X. D., Liu, H. F., & Zhang, X. (2011). The Relationship between area factors and enterprise's performance: An empirical study based on 52 areas' manufacturing enterprises in China. *Chinese Journal of Management*, 8(6), 827-836.